

DEMOCRATIC SCHOOL MANAGEMENT IN CURRENT EDUCATION: PARTICIPATION, COMMUNICATION AND MEDIATION

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Abstract

School management plays an extremely important role in any educational institution. The objective of this work is to identify the main challenges for the exercise of school management in a participatory and democratic way. Research was carried out on the main aspects involved in the exercise of educational management. It was concluded that, together with the school community, the manager is responsible for the good progress of the school, being under his care the administrative and pedagogical part, among the various problems that occur in daily life.

Keywords: School management. Participatory. Democratic.

Introduction

Democratic school management is essential for the proper functioning of any school. This management must be participatory, so that all sectors of the institution, such as faculty and students, other employees and the school community can act in the processes and in the daily life of the school.

The figure of authoritarian and centralizing management, frequent in older times, ends up disappearing from current institutions, although there are still directors who are adept at this management model. In this scenario, acts of abuse of power or creation of “benefits” for certain groups should be in the past.

Managers must make their decisions guided by pedagogical criteria, providing improvements for the teaching-learning process, and the smooth running of the school. Vaz (2008) reports that the fundamental activities for management must be considered together, to deliver to the target audience a better quality of the product or service.

Theoretical Reference

2.1. School Management understood as an element of counter-hegemony

Pereira (2018) proposes to integrate individual goals (of the worker) and business goals, focusing on a more participative and innovative management. From this perspective, the director must be aware of his posture and the pedagogical political project. This political pedagogical project must be seen as an ongoing and adaptive process and not just a legal obligation.

According to Betlinski (2013), public spaces for participation have the possibility of generating democratic management, which will depend on the culture and political project adopted by individuals who exercise coordination functions or members of their collegiate bodies. The manager should not have the attitude of one who solves everything and carries all the school's truths, he should respect the culture and opinions of that particular group.

The management must, yes, have rigor, critical sense, coherence and determination when solving a certain issue or problem in the institution. However, in other situations, relying on the support of the team can be quite advantageous, considering that this team is composed of people with different personalities, experiences and backgrounds, favoring the decision-making process.

In the pedagogical political project, the manager must establish and follow, together with the entire school community, a global plan with the posture, goals and work to be developed by the institution as a whole, dialoguing with the internal and external school community, seeking to bring education quality and solid citizen training.

Bartnik (p. 16, 2012) says that “educational management, especially democratic management, understood as an element of counter-hegemony, opposes the direct and uncritical implementation of administrative principles of business management in school organization”. In this context, the contribution of teachers, employees, students and their families is essential for the success of school management.

The family that participates and is active, manages to look at the school in a different way, participating in the results and encouraging students to also be active in that environment. In this way, when students become allies of the school, it opens doors for them to gain responsibilities and awaken administrative and organizational skills.

When management is democratic and participatory, it tends to be a model for transforming the reality of Education. For this to happen, it is necessary the commitment of all sectors of the institution, with full knowledge of the educational process, including the backstage of the classroom, seeking the progress of teaching.

2.2. Current Education and the Challenges of School Management

Libâneo (2004) points to a necessary readjustment of school processes in view of a new model of current Education. In contemporary society, one of the aspects observed is the continuous evolution of information and communication technologies (ICTs), which influence and cause changes in the forms of production in all areas of society.

Schaff (1992), Lévy (1995), Castells (2001) and Silveira (2019) state that new technologies such as the computer and the Internet provide changes in political, social and economic, educational and cultural contexts.

Currently, Education goes far beyond blackboard, chalk and books. This is no longer enough. Even the academic training of the teacher is no longer enough for him to carry out his profession to its end. It is necessary for the teacher to invest in continuing education and training linked to all the progress that the internet and technology can bring to the teaching-learning process.

The current challenge for the teaching profession is to create educational strategies that are really meaningful to students, in order to attract their attention to their studies. In this context, as highlighted by Lévy (1995), there are several experiences that demonstrate that the insertion of digital resources that are part of Web 2.0, when used in a well-planned, strategic way, can help achieve learning goals.

School management must be aware of all these changes that are taking place all the time. The novelties present can help in the evolution process of the school environment, in addition to contributing to the achievement of better pedagogical results and preparing to deal with the new challenges that arise in the daily life of the school community.

Managers must maintain a posture of support and collaboration so that their faculty can keep up to date through training, courses, lectures, workshops, seminars and congresses. These new experiences make the school environment updated and in tune with what is happening in the world.

2.3. Participatory Democratic School Management

During life, all people have the opportunity to experience different types of relationships: family, affective, friendship, among others. It is often not noticed the great importance of having these relationships for life to pass more easily. This type of relationship is called by Figaro (2008) interpersonal relationship.

Most of the time, people spend in the work environment. Establishing a good relationship between co-workers, generating a more pleasant relationship is a way to build a pleasant organizational climate so that activities occur normally and successfully. When the work environment is an educational institution, all of this must be thought through with greater attention.

The school is an environment with multiple types and styles of people who carry out their activities there, in addition to the constant coexistence with different students of various ages. In this environment of great diversity of thoughts and opinions, the possibilities of conflicting ideas are great.

Teachers, staff and even students have their worldviews based on their experiences. Differences in thoughts and ways of acting in certain cases directly influence decision making and problem solving. These individual differences cause conflict, generating incompatibility and differences in the interpretation of facts (MALAKOWSKY and KASSICK, 2014).

Conflicts need to be managed effectively, so that possibilities for action, growth and development are created, without affecting productivity and good interactions in the work environment. In this context, school management must seek ways to effectively participate in all sectors involved.

2.4. Interpersonal Relations in the Workplace

Bispo (2006) reports that in a problematic organizational climate, the team becomes unmotivated, frustrated, and there is a lack of mutual credibility between the institution and the employees. As a result, this process leads to the loss of talent, unproductiveness and little adaptation to changes, and we can also mention the high turnover and abstention and little dedication. Management must work so that this type of climate does not occur in the institution.

Silva (2001) reports that management must create conditions under which people can work willingly and voluntarily, towards the organization's goals, because, by enjoying their work, they will have a greater possibility of feeling the importance of doing it well. . Under these conditions, the entire team will be creating a good and productive organizational climate.

Management obtains its due success when it works with the participation of all people who are directly or entirely involved in the work processes, whether they are employees (teachers and other employees), or those benefiting from the services provided, in this case, students.

All experiences, experiences and suggestions from all parties bring benefits and for solving everyday problems. The manager must always keep in touch with all this team for this to happen. Communication is essential for the institution to develop well and have a good relationship with its public and its team.

According to Silva (2001), “to create an organizational climate that encourages people to work together, it is up to school administrators to emphasize the value of teamwork”. In this sense, it is very important that the manager has the ability to mediate the environment's conflicts, seeking dialogue with everyone involved in the student's education process: teachers, parents, school community and, of course, the student himself.

Management must know how to listen to everyone, sharing responsibilities and managing conflicts, making it possible to carry out a truly efficient and humanized management. For this, such manager must have knowledge of the whole reality of the school, always trying to keep up to date.

Managers also need to refresh their academic knowledge, participate in courses, symposia, improve people and process management techniques, in addition to always being informed about new technologies. A good school manager must, above all, believe in the transforming capacity of Education.

Management, teachers, staff, students, parents and the entire school community must create a peaceful and pleasant organizational climate. The union of all parts creates not only a better climate, but also better conditions for a quality education for all.

2.5. Management, Communication and Mediation

The school environment includes professionals from different backgrounds and levels of education. According to their area of training or even aspects related to their own personality, each professional presents their own way of being, thinking and working.

People differ in the way they think and act in certain cases, which directly influences decision making and problem solving. These individual differences cause conflict, generating incompatibility and differences in interpretation of the facts.

Conflicts need to be handled effectively, so that possibilities for action, growth and development are created, without affecting the productivity and desirable development of the school. For this to happen, the manager must be aware of communication methods, as mentioned by Barros (2014).

Communication provides greater efficiency in the team, in addition to resolving or reducing conflicts present in that environment. Through communication, the manager must develop methods and strategies for measurement. Mediation is the most effective and fastest method to deal with conflicts that exist in our environment, whether professional or community.

The manager, when acting as a mediator, must use their knowledge and resources to act in different types of conflict, as a way to help the parties involved to communicate more adequately so that they can reach a conciliatory understanding.

Team meetings and feedbacks are fundamental so that issues, criticisms and ideas can be debated clearly, without interference, thus enabling mediation to take place. Although the school manager has experience, he can and should rely on his entire team, which is made up of professionals specialized in their areas of expertise. With this, all experiences and experiences are used.

Barros (2014) emphasizes that mediation is a flexible process and can be adapted to the specific needs of a school center, taking into account the nature of conflicts and the purpose of the program. Mediation strategies are a great tool to improve coexistence in the environment and in the school community and should be adopted by all educational institutions.

According to Iungman (1996), the goals of school mediation should be based on building a stronger sense of cooperation and community with the school, developing critical thinking and problem-solving skills. In this sense, it should seek to favor the increase of self-esteem of members of the school community and facilitate communication and skills for daily life.

Discussions

The decentralization of management is a very positive factor for its realignment. Seeking the participation of all sectors of the educational institution and the entire community is extremely important. The division of responsibilities and the delegation of simple decisions to employees. With that, the results will have improvements in both the administrative and the pedagogical part.

It is necessary that the realignment of school management is based on the adaptation of work processes, so that the school team is prepared to work with new technological tools and the information and communication technologies themselves. In addition, all staff must be engaged so that the rights and duties of students, teachers and other staff are respected.

The teacher must have greater respect and appreciation before the population and all professional classes, considering that any profession was based on the figure of the teacher in

guidance. Students, in turn, have the right guaranteed by law to have quality education, in addition to academic and citizenship training in accordance with the school's values.

Furthermore, participatory and democratic management must be open to suggestions and criticism, enabling the success of such management not to be a merit or achievement of the professional manager, but the success of the entire internal and external school community, taking as a reference, the realignment based on innovation and institution improvement.

Conclusions

The pacification and democratization of the school can be achieved through mediation. The organizational climate tends to become better with mediation, since the improvement in the environment allows the educational community to learn to deal with conflicts in a more efficient way. All these aspects must be carried out respecting the school's differences and diversities.

According to Almeida (2009), it is necessary to deal with the conflict through creative and cooperative solutions, replacing the win-lose paradigm with the win-win paradigm, providing mutual satisfaction to the dissenting parties. Dialogue must be present at all stages of mediation.

A participatory and democratic management can only be built when its bases are constituted with dialogue, communication and mediation of environmental problems. A pleasant organizational climate is a key factor for any company, but when the organization is an educational institution, care must be greater.

Management must maintain guidelines aimed at its decentralization, as well as prioritizing the needs of the student; valuing teaching professionals and other employees, constant improvement through continuing education, and automation of processes with information and communication technologies.

Good management is successful through well-planned and organized processes, noting the need for constant evaluation of this process. At a time when the management is successful, the gains are not only for the individual who holds the position, but for the entire community involved, with parents, staff and teachers in a harmonious relationship, aiming at the effective academic and civic education of today's students, which represent the future of the nation.

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